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Agent-Based Modeling of Ukraine's Organizations' Response to Full-Scale russian Invasion of Ukraine

The russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 created challenges for organizational adaptation. Ukrainian organizations faced a prolonged crisis that required managing survival, continuity, and transformation. Research with 22 Ukrainian organizations showed that most experienced operational disruption from which they recovered within two months, then transformed their operations to function under new conditions (Serdyuk, 2023). Agent-based modeling captures emergent behaviors from agent interactions under varying rules and constraints, but most models were developed for stable environments or short-term disruptions. This paper analyzes agent-based organizational models, evaluating their applicability to prolonged conflict situations with distinct phases and multiple demand types.

To evaluate the applicability of existing models to the Ukrainian context, we first establish the theoretical foundations of organizational adaptation to disasters. Organizations respond to disruptions in different ways. The Disaster Research Center typology describes four types of responses to a disruption (Dynes, 1970). Established responses occur when no changes in organizational structure happen. Expanding responses require more resources to accomplish the same tasks. Extending responses occur when an organization adds new parts that extend its functions. Emerging responses appear when new structural forms and tasks emerge to cope with the disruption.

Gary Kreps proposed a structural approach based on four elements where domains and tasks represent the structural ends of the organization, while resources and activities represent the structural means (Kreps & Bosworth, 2007). In regular situations, an organization forms from domains to tasks to resources to activities in D-T-R-A order. During disruption, the order inverts to A-R-T-D, moving from actions relevant in the emergency situation to resources, with later structuration into corresponding tasks and new domains.

When a disaster disrupts organizational operations, it brings to life new demands. Researchers distinguish demands generated by a disaster agent and those caused by an organization's efforts to manage the disaster (Quarantelli, 1997). The first are called agent-generated demands, and the second are response-generated demands. Agent-generated demands require a tactical or contingency approach because they are specific to the disaster agent, and responses can only be partly anticipated beforehand (Quarantelli, 1997). Response-generated demands could

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potentially be foreseen and should be included in organizational contingency planning.

Research on 22 Ukrainian organizations revealed adaptation challenges differing from single-shock disasters assumed by most models (Serdyuk, 2023). Most organizations recovered operationally within two months, transforming the initial crisis into operations under new conditions.

Six demand classes emerged. Agent-generated demands («army support» and «employee safety») arising from the invasion are represented by military responses structured into roles within 2-3 months; safety required improvisation beyond the COVID-19 experience. Response-generated demands («stressed people» and «social responsibility») emerged from disaster management, such as burnout support and conscription obligations, enabled repurposing COVID-19 structures. HR roles expanded dramatically. Environment-generated demands («cost cutting» and «new markets») resulted from market shrinking, supply chain breakdown, and personnel shortage.

Responses aligned with DRC typology (Dynes, 1970): established structures maintained routines; expanding structures added resources; extending structures created new divisions; emergent structures formed novel arrangements (military suppliers, volunteer networks, dual-mode operations). The A-R-T-D sequence (Kreps & Bosworth, 2007) formalized improvised activities into permanent domains.

Adaptation unfolded across distinct phases. Immediate phase (February–April 2022): crisis response with 10 million displaced; agent-generated demands primed responses. Acute phase (April–October 2022): sustained resistance, infrastructure repair, balancing continuity with military support; agent-generated demands prevailed. Chronic phase (November 2022–2024): dual-mode operations; response-generated demands prevailed (Serdyuk, 2023). Recovery phase (future): reconstruction and transformation. Unlike natural disasters, which have sequential phases, invasion requires the simultaneous management of survival, resistance, and planning. Each phase exhibits distinct patterns of agent-generated versus response-generated demand. Existing agent-based models partially address Ukrainian organizational adaptation patterns but have significant gaps.

Epstein's model (2003, implemented by Hall, 2012) treats organizations as hierarchies with 20-parameter genomes that shift between flat (market) and tall (command-and-control structures) based on environmental demands. Hybrid objectives produce oscillating rather than stable configurations. This illuminates the bottom-up restructuring of Ukrainian organizations and their shifting between normal and crisis modes, but fails to capture the war-phase dynamics, the distinction between agent-generated and response-generated demands, or the formalization of improvisation into permanent structures.

SKIN (Gilbert, Pyka, & Ahrweiler, 2001) models adaptation through knowledge structures («kenes») and innovation. Firms pursue incremental or radical research and form partnerships around complementary knowledge. Calibrated with 21 parameters against telecommunications/biotechnology cases, it

found that policy affects network evolution and multiple disaster-response networks form naturally. This explains the emergence and adaptation strategy diffusion of volunteer coordination. The radical distinction parallels repurposing COVID-19 protocols versus military supplier transformations. However, SKIN lacks crisis response mechanisms, hierarchical coordination structures, and phase-dependent adaptation logic.

WorkSim (Kant, Ballot, & Goudet, 2020) represents labor market dynamics using 56 parameters that match 63 French targets, reproducing the Beveridge, Phillips, and Okun curves. It emphasizes institutional importance and contract segmentation. This provides insights into retention challenges, conscription impacts, and dual labor arrangements during a crisis. However, it assumes stable environments, lacks crisis mechanisms, and provides limited representation of organizational structure.

EURACE simulates European economies with heterogeneous agents across regions, illustrating how local interactions give rise to macroeconomic phenomena. However, computational complexity and treating firms as production functions rather than adaptive organizations limit applicability.

All models overlook the distinction between agent-generated and response-generated demand, which is fundamental to Ukrainian decision-making (Serdyuk, 2023). They assume short-term disruption rather than multi-phase conflict, ignore adversarial environments opposing adaptation, exclude international intervention dimensions, cannot manage overlapping survival-to-planning timeframes, and lack representation of the formalization process (improvisation – resources – tasks – domains).

Given the gaps identified in existing models, we propose a NetLogo model that addresses these limitations by integrating features specific to prolonged military conflict. The event flow of the proposed model is shown in Figure 1.

The model simulates Ukrainian organizational adaptation through six agent types representing organizations, demands, resources, volunteers, state actors, and international actors. Organizations are classified according to the DRC typology, as established, expanding, extending, or emergent, based on demand pressure and resource strain, rather than being assigned to fixed categories. The model implements mechanisms absent from existing approaches. The A-R-T-D process tracks progression from improvised activities through resource mobilization and task formalization to domain establishment, with entries moving from activities to tasks to domains as formalization occurs. Phase-dependent adaptation modifies environmental parameters across the immediate, acute, chronic, and recovery phases, with transitions altering threat levels, international support availability, and the intensity of market disruption. Dual demand processing allows organizations to handle agent-generated and response-generated demands using different priority rules, with agent-generated demands receiving priority in the immediate and acute phases. The model captures the formation of volunteer networks, organizational partnerships based on trust and proximity, international support networks with bureaucratic delays, and state coordination networks based on priority alignment.

Fig. 1. Event Flow of the Ukrainian Organizations' NetLogo Model

The model is calibrated qualitatively to match patterns from research with 22 Ukrainian organizations (Serdyuk, 2023), including recovery time distribution with most organizations recovering within two months, phase transition timing, demand type distribution with agent-generated demands concentrated in immediate and acute phases, and adaptation success rates varying by demand type with higher success for familiar demands where COVID-19 protocols could be repurposed.

The proposed NetLogo model advances organizational adaptation theory by synthesizing multiple perspectives within an architecture grounded in Ukrainian reality. By integrating phase-dependent environmental dynamics, dual demand processing with different priority rules by phase, structure classification based on real-time conditions, and formalization tracking, the model captures complexity absent from existing frameworks. The model explains phenomena such as HR domain expansion, COVID-19 protocol reuse, formalization of military support, and dual-mode operation that emerge from Ukrainian organizational experiences.

Further research should focus on calibrating and validating the model on data from the further phases of the war. This would allow for testing the model's predictive capacity and refining its mechanisms based on organizational adaptation patterns that emerge in later stages of the conflict.

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